

ISic0963

I.Sicily inscription 0963

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica, inventory 2257

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἄλφ(ιος) Κλω̄δης ἐτελεύτησεν πρὸ η εἰδ(ῶν)
2. Νοβेम(βρίων) ἡμέρ(α) Ἡλίου υἱὸς Λουκίου καὶ
3. Καικει[λί]ας τῶν κειμένων ἰς τὸν πυ[λῶ][να]
4. ἰσερχομένων ἰς δεξιὰ ἄρξας τὴν δευτέ
5. ραν ἀρχὴν καὶ πρε[σ]βίας πρεσβεύ[σ]ας πρὸς
6. βασιλέα καὶ γ παραπονπῆς·
7. ἔζησ(εν) ἔτη λα μῆνες ι ἡμέ(ραι) κα

Apparatus

Text of PHI, after IG XIV.235

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492683

EDCS 39102210

PHI 140535

PHI 175470

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0235 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5465
- Cagnat, R., Toutain, J., Jouguet, P. 1906-1927. *Inscriptiones Graecae ad res Romanas pertinentes*. Paris. At 497
- Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.37 ph
- Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.63
- Manganaro, G. 1961. Iscrizioni di Adrano. *PdP*. 16: 126-135. At 130 n.13
- Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 142-143
- Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 36-37 tav.IX.15
- Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.490

Licensed under a Creative Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0963. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340204>